

INTELLIGENT ROUND ROBIN SCHEDULING ALGORITHM WITH DYNAMIC TIME QUANTUM

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Abstract:

In this paper, we have studied various algorithms for scheduling of the processes in Operating System (OS). Amongst all the algorithms, Round Robin (RR) performs optimally in timeshared system because each process is given an equal amount of static time quantum. But the effectiveness of RR algorithm solely depends upon the choice of time quantum. We have made a comprehensive study and analysis of RR algorithm. We have proposed a new Improved-RR algorithm Intelligent RR (Intelligent Round Robin) by using Intelligent Time Slice. Our experimental analysis shows that Intelligent RR performs better than RR algorithm in terms of reducing the number of context switches, average waiting time and average turnaround time.

Keywords: Operating System, Scheduling Algorithm, Round Robin, Context switch, Waiting time, Turnaround time.

Introduction

An operating system is a program that acts as an interface between the user and the computer hardware and controls the execution of all kinds of programs.

Fig.1

Operating systems are there from the very first computer generation. Operating systems keep evolving over the period of time. Following are few of the important types of operating system which are most commonly used. Batch operating system, Time-sharing operating systems, Distributed operating System, Network operating System and Real Time operating System.

A process is a program in execution. The execution of a process must progress in a sequential fashion. As a process executes, it changes state. The state of a process is defined as the current activity of the process.

Fig.2

Each process is represented in the operating system by a process control block (PCB) also called a task control block. PCB is the data structure used by the operating system. Operating system groups all information that needs about particular process. The process scheduling is the activity of the process manager that handles the removal of the running process from the CPU and the selection of another process on the basis of a particular strategy. Process scheduling is an essential part of a Multiprogramming operating system. Such operating systems allow more than one process to be loaded into the executable memory at a time and loaded process shares the CPU using time multiplexing. Scheduling algorithms are widely used in operating systems to allocate resources to competing tasks. In operating systems, the scheduler must order the set of running processes for access to the CPU and other system resources. The aim of process scheduling is to assign the processor or processors to the set of processes in a way that meets system and user objectives such as response time, throughput or processor efficiency. This research investigates several well known CPU scheduling algorithms by means of analysis and compares their performance under different workloads.

Scheduling Algorithms

The CPU scheduler executes the processes when they schedules on it. When there are number of processes in the ready queue, the algorithm which decides the order of execution of those processes is called *scheduling algorithm*. The various well known CPU scheduling algorithms are First Come First Serve (FCFS), Shortest Job First (SJF) and Priority scheduling. All the above algorithms are non-preemptive in nature and are not suitable for time sharing systems. Shortest Remaining Time First (SRTF) and Round Robin (RR) are preemptive in nature. RR is most suitable for time sharing systems.

EXISTING CPU SCHEDULING ALGORITHMS

There are many CPU Scheduling algorithms but some of them which are commonly used are explained below.

First-Come, First-Served (FCFS): This algorithm allocates the CPU to the process that requests the CPU first. This algorithm is easily managed with a FIFO queue. New process enters the queue through the tail of the queue and leaves through the head of the queue (when the process is allocated to the CPU). The processes are allocated to the CPU on the basis of their arrival at the queue. Once a process is allocated to the CPU, it is removed from the queue. A process does not give up CPU until it either terminates or performs IO.

Shortest-Job-First (SJF): The SJF algorithm associates the length of the next CPU burst with each processes such that that the process that have the smallest next CPU burst is allocated to the CPU. The SJF uses the FCFS to break tie (a situation where two processes have the same length next CPU burst). The SJF algorithm may be implemented as either a preemptive or non-preemptive algorithms. When the execution of a process that is currently running is interrupted in order to give the CPU to a new process with a shorter next CPU burst, it is called a preemptive SJF. On the other hand, the non-preemptive SJF will allow the currently running process to finish its CPU burst before a new process is allocated to the CPU.

Priority Scheduling (PS): The PS algorithm associates with each process a priority and the CPU is allocated to the process based on their priorities. Usually, lower numbers are used to represent higher priorities. The process with the highest priority is allocated first. If there are multiple processes with same priority, typically the FCFS is used to break tie.

Round Robin (RR): The RR algorithm is designed especially for Real time systems and is similar to the FCFS algorithm. Here, a small unit of time (called time quantum or time slice) is defined. A time quantum is generally from 10-100 milliseconds. So, the RR algorithm will allow the first process in the queue to run until it expires its quantum (i.e. runs for as long as the time quantum), then run the next process in the queue for the duration of the same time quantum. The RR keeps the ready processes as a FIFO queue. So, new processes are added to the tail of the queue. Depending on the time quantum and the CPU burst requirement of each process, a process may need less than or more than a time quantum to execute on the CPU. In a situation where the process

need more than a time quantum, the process runs for the full length of the time quantum and then it is preempted. The preempted process is then added to the tail of the queue again but with its CPU burst now a time quantum less than its previous CPU burst. This continues until the execution of the process is completed. The RR algorithm is naturally preemptive. Disadvantages of RR

- Allocating equal amounts of time to each task is simple, but it can frustrate users when it comes to medium-length tasks.
- Frequent context switching increases overheads in case of small time quantum.
- When time quantum increases the scheduling is as same as the FCFS.

Scheduling Objectives: A system designer must consider a variety of factors in designing a scheduling algorithm, such as type of systems used and what are user's needs. Depending on the system, the user and designer might expect the scheduler to find an optimal resource usage schedule.

Maximize throughput: A scheduling algorithm should be capable of servicing the maximum number of processes per unit of time.

Avoid indefinite blocking or starvation: A process should not wait for unbounded time before or while process service.

Minimize overhead: Overhead causes wastage of resources. But when we use system resources effectively, then overall system performance improves greatly.

Enforcement of priorities: if system assigns priorities to processes, the scheduling mechanism should favor the Higher-priority processes.

Achieve balance between response and utilization: The scheduling mechanism should keep resources of system busy. Favor processes exhibits desirable behavior. Degrade gracefully under heavy load. A system can accomplish these goals in several ways. The scheduler can prevent indefinite blocking of processes through the concept of aging. The scheduler can increase throughput by favoring processes whose requests can be satisfied quickly, or whose completion cause other processes to run.

Proposed Round Robin with Intelligent Time Slicing

1. Start
2. First of all check ready queue is empty
3. Processes are assigned into the ready queue.
4. All the processes are rearranged in increasing order that means smaller burst time process get higher priority and larger burst time process get lower priority.
5. While (ready queue != NULL)
6. Calculate Intelligent Time Slice: Intelligent Time Slice = Average of burst time of all processes in the ready queue
7. While (total number of processes in the ready queue>0)
8. Assign intelligent time slice to the i^{th} process in ready queue($i=1,2,3,\dots,n$, n =number of process)
count=count+1
9. If (Number of process in ready queue > 0) then go to step 5
10. If a new process is arrived update the ready queue, go to step 4.
11. End of While
12. Calculate average waiting time, turnaround time, context switches and throughput.
13. End

Experimental Analysis

To evaluate the performance of proposed algorithm, we have taken a set of processes in different cases. Here for simplicity, we have taken 5 or 4 processes. The algorithm works effectively even if it used with a very large number of processes. In each case, we have compared the experimental results of proposed algorithm with the Simple Round Robin Scheduling Algorithm with fixed time quantum Q. Here we have assumed a constant time quantum Q for simple RR and compare with the result. In the following calculation we have varied the intelligent time slice depending on the number of processes. The smart time slice can be calculated according to proposed plan.

Case 1:

We Assume five processes arriving at time = 0, with increasing burst time (P1 = 14, P2 = 34, P3 = 45, P4 = 62, P5 = 77) with time quantum =25 as shown in Table.1. The Table.1 shows the output using RR algorithm and Intelligent RR algorithm. The following figures show Gantt chart for both the

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algorithms simple RR and Intelligent RR respectively.

Processes	Arrival Time	CPU Burst time
P1	0	14
P2	0	34
P3	0	45
P4	0	62
P5	0	77

Table.1

According to simple RR

P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P2	P3	P4	P5	P4	P5	P5	
0	14	39	64	89	114	123	143	168	193	205	230	232

Proposed mechanism

First of all arrange the processes in ready queue according their given burst time in increasing order that is P1=14, P2=34, P3=45, P4=62 and P5=77 and after that choose the time quantum according Intelligent RR algorithm, the time quantum is the average of the burst time of the processes in the job queue. This is repeated each time the processor completes one Time Quantum for all the processes. Here the TQ for the first iteration is 46.4. The Gantt chart for Intelligent RR,

P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P4	P5	P5	
0	14	48	93	139.4	185.8	201.4	224.5	232

Algorithm	Time Quantum	Average WT	Average TAT	Throughput
Simple RR	25	97	143.4	low
Intelligent RR	TQ1=46.4 TQ2=23.1 TQ3=7.5	71.28	117.28	high

Case 2:

Assume that 4 processes arrives at time =0, with burst time(P1=8,P2=12,P3=16,P4=10) with time quantum=5

Processes	Arrival Time	Burst Time(ms)
P1	0	8
P2	0	12
P3	0	16
P4	0	10

Table.2

According to simple RR

P1	P2	P3	P4	P1	P2	P3	P4	P2	P3	P3	
0	5	10	15	20	23	28	33	38	40	45	46

Proposed mechanism

First of all arrange the processes in ready queue according their given burst time in increasing order that is P1=8, P2=10, P3=12 and P4=16 and after that choose the time quantum according Intelligent RR algorithm, the time quantum is the average of the burst time of the processes in the job queue. This is repeated each time the processor completes one Time Quantum for all the processes. Here the TQ for the first iteration is 11.5. The Gantt chart for Intelligent RR,

P1	P4	P2	P3	P2	P3	P3	
0	8	18	29.5	41	41.5	44	46

Algorithm	Time Quantum	Average WT	Average TAT	Throughput
Simple RR	5	25.25	36.5	low
Intelligent RR	TQ1=11.5 TQ2=2.5 TQ3=2	16.875	28.375	high

Conclusion

We have successfully compared both the algorithm i.e. simple round robin and the proposed one that the proposed one is more efficient because it has less average waiting time, average turnaround time and number of context switches as compared to simple round robin, in turn reducing the operating system overhead and hence dispatch latency. Also, it reduces the problem of starvation as the processes with less remaining CPU burst time are assigned with the higher priorities and are executed first in the

second round of algorithm. Performance of time sharing systems can be improved with the proposed algorithm and can also be modified to enhance the performance of real time system.

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